

Culture and Tradition in Anita Nair's 'Ladies Coupe'

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ABSTRACT

Culture is the most important for the construction of any society. Social interactions are within the culture is a characteristics feature of any society. Culture gives the social identity for a group of people on which a person can make his individual identity. It is made by the people and it taught for the people. Everybody feel proud of their own culture and traditions. Culture is a base of Society which is combination of customs, rituals, and idea for behaviour, belief, values, attitude and the meaning of behaviour. Culture differs from one another society and community. The present paper attempt to search the different culture and tradition presented in Anita Nair's book 'Ladies Coupe'. This culture which is for the people who construct their identity with him forced to women, lost their identity, freedom and desire. Ladies Coupe is the fine example of the cultural and traditional things which became a mental trauma for the may of characters. Akhila, Marikonathu, Prabha Devi, Janki and Seela are some of characters with which Anita Nair elaborate te victimization of subordinate and marginal people.

KEYWORDS: Marginality Culture, Subjugation, Spinster

INTRODUCTION

Culture is a way of behaviour where which people find the right direction to render his life in the society. This is a practice of people living in a group where people living with specific idea social custom and belief in a particular group of people. In India there are many different culture people are living together and following their different and unique culture and tradition. People celebrating Eid, Diwali and Christmas which are the occasion of different festivals of different religion. Different religion differs with different culture and tradition and so with the way of behaviour and the way of following of this system. Indian writing in English is rich with different types of cultural variety of the description. They elaborated this with the words and described the vivid description of the different culture with different perspectives.

Life and Work of Anita Nair:-

Anita Nair uses the term culture through her many novels. As she born in Kerala which blessed the beauty of nature and rich with the cultural tradition Kerala became base for her many writings. She was born in Mundakottakurissi near Sharnur on 26 Jan 1966. She published her first book of collection of short stories 'Satyr of the Subway' which won her prestigious fellowship of 'Virginia Centre for the Creative Arts' in 1997 she moved to Virginia centre for pursuing her further education in Creative Arts in 1998. Her first novel The Better Man was bestselling published in 1999 and Ladies Coupe in 2001 both bestselling and translated in to many different languages. She lives in Bangalore and

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frequently visits to Kerala where she had her grandmother so Kerala and Karnataka culture describe in her many novels. Sometimes this culture and tradition became the boundary which create the marginality and became the reason of subjugation of marginal people.

'I by no means intend to simplify the challenges women face in any culture. Women are marginality in all cultures in my opinion, some in more extreme ways than others.'

Zainab Salbi

As stated by Zainab Salbi culture which is rich with custom and tradition becomes the shackle for the improvement for the marginal sect such as women, lower class people, lower caste people to be a part of mainstream society. Mainstream society such as male or upper caste people dominate with the way of attitude towards them.

Culture and Tradition in 'Ladies Coupe'

Marriage is a beautiful ceremony which combine two beautiful person physically, socially and emotionally. This ceremony is a combination of different customs and rituals. But culture makes compulsory for every women to undergo with this ceremony. As Akhila chief protagonist of the novel Ladies Coupe who is 45 spinster working as an income tax office clerk. Forced to do work because of circumstances. She lost her father when she was 19yrs old. So she became the earning source of the family. She perform all parental responsibilities for her siblings Padma, Narsimha and

Narayan their education and marriages. But in mean time she lost the age of her own marriage so society and her own relatives forced her to get married which make her frustrated. In the psychological trauma she ask a question can woman live single and live happy or a man must to complete her.

"I don't know if you will be able to help me but you must tell me what you think. Can a woman cope alone?"

Ladies coupe, 22

This is our culture that a girl should marry at a certain age and if not then society will not allow her to live alone. This is out from our cultural and traditional values of India. Society will not accept it easily that she is trying to live with her own norms. So she became a centre of blaming of people which always trap her in psychological state from where she could not get out from it. Anita Nair tries to mention the custom of this cultural ceremony when a girl's parent should be ready for marriage of her with some dowry. Akhila who is the only earning source of her family also made necessary arrangements for her younger sister Padma.

"Padma was Twenty-two by time Akhila put together a dowry for her. Gold jewellery, a diamond nose-stud; a steel almirah, a cot and a mattress; stainless steel and bronze cookware; silver lamps; a gold ring and an expensive wrist watch for the groom; and twenty thousand rupees in cash."

(Ladies coupe 78)

This is the common picture in our Indian culture and tradition that when a girl child is born parents worried for the dowry and the expectations of her would be -in -laws family. This makes a girl child dominated by main stream society. Even when Akhila just because of her parental responsibilities could not marry people and her own sister too thinking that she will ran away from home with someone surely.

"She's having a love affair. And she doesn't want us to find out. That's why she wants to find out. That's why she wants to go away by herself. Who is he? And how did you find him?"

Ladies Coupe 206

So likewise it is suspected that if a girl is elderly unmarried then there must be having her love affair. So throughout the novel Akhila is in search of the answer if women can live single or not. So with the frustrated mind she took up one way journey to Kanyakumari and boarded herself in the ladies compartment of the train.

Apart from this marriage Anita Nair beautifully demonstrate the culture of Brahmin Akhila who wish if she could take her mother for lunch outside her Amma insist to go in Dasaprakash Hotel. Her mother thinks that this is a hotel where only Brahmin cook, chop and serve. So even Akhila don't likes the food serve there they went in the same hotel. "What is wrong in Dasaprakash? It is one place where Brahmins can eat without worrying about who's doing the chopping and cooking or even the washing-up."

"To Amma, all waiters were boys and all Brahmins above reproach."

Ladies Coupe 79

Janaki is a women whom she met in her journeys who is pampered daughter, obedient wife and cared mother she is as like in our Hindu culture said a woman must be. She tried very hard to be a good wife and mother. Our culture said to give extra treatment to a girl child and so she was always been looked after. She was believed that duty of a woman is to get married and obey the instructions of her husband and in-laws. Because he knows better what is good for her so she believed that a home is the kingdom of a woman so she never even think out of it which I actually Hindu culture said for a woman about. According to our tradition a woman must be in four wall of home, she is responsible for child and the old people in her home for looking after them. She should take care of everybody's like and dislikes and all. In the process of being good to all and treat like a princess she lost her self and think if any time I lost this all can I cope alone. She is tired of being always cared by someone.

"I was tired of being this fragile creature."

Ladies Coupe 23

Like Janaki Margaret Shanthi was a passenger of Akhila who is also victim of social cultural system of India. She is chemistry teacher working in a school where her husband is working as a principal. When she brought up she told by her mother that husband knows better what is good for you so even if you don't want to do anything then also never say no. She wished to peruse PhD but her husband Ebenezer Paulraj said no she gave up, she wished for long hair but cut it off because Ebe doesn't like that most important sacrifice she did that is MTP. When she got pregnant she want to become mother but her husband a baby that time so he forced to abort the pregnancy . She could not speak a word against it but only tears came down. As our culture says woman should obey the husband as he is a God for her. He is the master of her and so whatever he says she should listen.

Marikolanthu is another victim picturised by Anita Nair of this cultural system of India. She is working at a landlord family of the village one of the relative of the family Murugan physically assaults her and leave her to get unwed mother. Her mother was so afraid how can she get married now whom will be ready to marry her and how could she gets 'Husband's Protection'. This phrase cringe Marikonathu as her father died years ago and Sujata akka's husband also not so looked after for them then why this husband's protection is important for a woman. Apart from this Anita Nair demonstrated the festival Pongal and Deepavali, some ritual kanakabharanam, some traditional cloths of Kerala pavadai and Veshti represents the cultural richness of Kerala tradition.

Anita Nair represented a perfect cultured women with the Akhila's mother who is obedient wife and everything she does according to the wish of her husband. She never allow anybody from home to fold his cloths or do his work she use to do it all alone saying he likes to do all these on mine. As Akhila knows her father doesn't even bother who is doing the work but she always fulfil all the needs of her husband . as our culture said that an obedient wife should do everything of her husband and take care of his likes and dislikes she perfectly did it all for him. Anitha Nair simultaneously with Hindu tradition picturises the christen characters like Kathrin Margaret , Missy K and Missy V beautifully.

Conclusion:-

Anita Nair demonstrate Culture and tradition of Kerala very beautifully. Culture is a back bone of society and people feel proud for the richness of it. The culture is actually is a way of behaviour and that is actually for good for the society but sometimes it became the reason for the subjugation of the women. Indirectly they get exploited in it.

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